

16th Jenner Glycobiology and Medicine Symposium

Report by: Aisha Jamal and Dr. Róisín O'Flaherty

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Organising Committee: Dr. Róisín O'Flaherty (Chairperson)^{a,b,c,#,*}, Dr. Gordon Greville^{d,*}, Dr. Nezira Delagic^{c,d,*}, Dr. Trinidad Velasco-Torrijos^{a,c,*}, Dr. Catherine Bannon^{c,d,*}, Andreea Cislaru^{a,*}, Emily Harlin^{a,*}, Ismail Emre Yağmur^{a,c,*}, Aine O'Brien^{a,*}, Elizabeth Rozeboom^{a,*}, Barbara Woods^{a,*}, Aisha Jamal^{a,b,*}, Prof. John Axford^{e,#}, Prof. Pauline Rudd^{f,#}, Prof. Ceslo A. Reis^{g,#}, Prof. Henrik Clausen^{h,#}, Prof. Claudine Kieda^{i,#}, Dr. Katrine Schjoldager^{j,#}, Prof. Nico Callewaert^{k,#}, Prof. Ghislain Opdenakker^{l,#}.

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*Organizing Committee #Scientific Committee

Event Sponsors: See list on final page of this Report

Summary

The 16th Jenner Glycobiology and Medicine Conference was held on 11-13 June 2025 in Maynooth University, Ireland. Chaired by Dr. Róisín O'Flaherty, the Scientific Committee aimed to provide an international forum for scientists and clinicians to disseminate the findings of current leading-edge research in the field of Glycoscience. The program was devoted to addressing and integrating different aspects of Glycoscience in physiological and pathological settings, including Chemistry, Immunology, Infection, Cancer and Neurological disorders. In addition to internationally renowned speakers, a number of poster and oral presentations were selected from the submitted abstracts, creating a stimulating discussion platform to address current and future challenges of Glycobiology and Glycotechnology.

This year we introduced the *Rising Stars in Glycoscience Satellite Conference* on 11 June 2025 at the National

Science and Ecclesiology Museum in Maynooth University before the start of 16th Jenner Glycobiology and Medicine Symposium to give a special opportunity for earlier career glycoscientists to present and learn from veterans in the field. The satellite event was chaired by Dr. Gordon Greville. It was free of charge to participants, and the aim was to bridge the gap between early career researchers and established experts, enhancing the early career researcher's professional development and networking opportunities.

Attendees

The 16th Jenner Glycobiology and Medicine Symposium has been attended by 220 delegates which includes researchers, clinicians, patient, industrialists, PhD and postdoc students. 180 delegates were international from countries around the world including France, Portugal, Denmark, Belgium, Netherlands, United States, Germany, Croatia, Austria, Japan, Czechia, UK, Poland, Canada, Switzerland, Sweden and Slovakia. A

glimpse of the event is available at the [16th Jenner Glycobiology and Medicine Symposium website](#).

Target audience: Academics, industrialists, clinicians, patients, early career researchers, postgraduate students

A selection of attendees at the 16th Jenner Glycobiology and Medicine Symposium in Maynooth University, Ireland. Front row comprises member of scientific committee and organising committee including chairperson Dr Roisin O'Flaherty (red).

Programme

The 16th Jenner Glycobiology and Medicine Symposium attendees were struck by the insights and discoveries of numerous researchers. Some speakers were at the initial stages of their career, and some had followed a long path in the field including Prof. Pauline Rudd, one of pioneers in the field of Glycobiology (one of the original and longstanding members of the Scientific Committee). Below is the list of sessions along with the name of researchers and their topics of interest.

Session 1: Sialic Acid Biology: From Tumour Immunity to Tissue Engineering

Yvette Van Kooyk , <i>Amsterdam UMC, The Netherlands</i>	Sialylation of the tumor microenvironment and its impact on immune suppression
Sandra van Vliet , <i>Amsterdam UMC, The Netherlands</i>	Site-specific reprogramming of the tumor-immune microenvironment through sialic acids
Jack Cheeseman , <i>Ludger Ltd, The United Kingdom</i>	Potential sialic acid and glycomic biomarkers of cardiovascular disease
Aert Scheper , <i>CÚRAM Research Ireland Centre for Medical Devices, Ireland</i>	IVD regeneration in a canine nucleus pulposus injury model – using sialylation inhibitor-loaded injectable hydrogels for IVD repair

Session 2: Glycosylation Pathways: Mechanisms and Modulators

Matthew Wilson , <i>KU Leuven, Belgium</i>	Revising dolichol biosynthesis: an unexpected detour
Frederic Bard , <i>Centre de Recherche en Cancérologie de Marseille, France</i>	ER O-glycosylation in synovial fibroblasts drives cartilage degradation
Mark Robinson , <i>Maynooth University, Ireland</i>	Assessing glycosylation enzyme expression in activated innate lymphocyte subpopulations
Qianyue Zhang , <i>Leiden University Medical Center, The Netherlands</i>	Obesity affects the adipocyte glycosylation machinery and N-glycan profiles in mice
Nele Festjens , <i>VIB-Ugent Center for Medical Biotechnology, Belgium</i>	N-glycosylation engineering in chimeric antigen receptor T cells enhances anti-tumor activity

Session 3: Mucosal Glycobiology: Roles of Mucins and O-Glycans in Disease

Gunnar C Hansson , <i>University of Gothenburg, Sweden</i>	The highly glycosylated mucins form different types of mucus that both inhibit and cause disease of the intestine and lung
Rajindra Aryal , <i>Harvard Medical School, USA</i>	Unravelling the role of extended O-glycans in human biology: insight from the pathogenic variants of C1GALT1C1
Rebecca Bennion , <i>Cancer Research Center of Marseille, France</i>	Defining ER-localised O-glycosylation in pancreatic ductal adenocarcinoma
Joseph J Barchi Jr , <i>Centre for Cancer Research</i>	(Ir)rational design of mucin glycopeptides as tumor immunotherapeutic agents

Session 4: Cancer Glycobiology

Mathieu Decloquement , <i>University of Alberta, Edmonton, Canada</i>	Deciphering siglec ligands in cancer to improve immunotherapy
Catarina Azevedo , <i>University of Porto, Porto, Portugal</i>	Glycoengineering of CD8+ T cell as a novel strategy to enhance T cell anti-tumor therapies

Ines Moreira, *Hannover Medical School, Germany* Neolactotetraosylceramide enables urinary detection of bladder cancer

Rafaela Abrantes, *University of Porto (i3S), Portugal* Novel CAR T formulations targeting tumor-associated glycoepitopes: a new strategy for solid tumors

Ana Magalhaes, *University of Porto (i3S), Portugal* Heparan and chondroitin sulfate proteoglycans cellular switch and functional implications for gastric cancer

Session 5: Glycosylation and Immune Modulation in Disease

Yusuke Mimura, *NHO Yamaguchi Ube Medical Center, Japan* Galactosylated and afucosylated glycoforms of intravenous immunoglobulin control inflammation

Cengiz Goekeri, *Charité - Universitätsmedizin Berlin, Germany* Unravelling the role of terminal fucosylation in Pneumococcal Pneumonia

Daniel Hornikx, *Radboud University, The Netherlands* Dissecting siglec-15 ligand expression in thyroid cancer

Padryk Merkyl, *ETH Zurich, Switzerland* Mucin degrading enzymes – a platform to study their activity

Shasha Li, *Queen's University Belfast, United Kingdom* Development and testing of novel small molecule inhibitors for the manipulation of IgE glycosylation

Session 6: Glycoimmune Modulation: Mechanistic Insights from GlycoRNA to Host-Pathogen Interactions

Ryan Flynn, *Harvard University, USA* GlycoRNA biology on the cell surface

Michelle Kilcoyne, *University of Galway, Ireland* Glycomics microarrays for profiling host immune-pathogen interactions and measuring adaptive immune response

Joana Gomes, *University of Porto (i3S), Portugal* ST6GAL1 role in antibody therapy response and immune evasion of colorectal cancer

Radka Fahey (Salдова), *NIBRT, Ireland* Endometriosis specific vaginal microbiota links to

urine and serum N-glycome

Session 7: Glycobiotechnology

Dr Tomas Carroll & Orla Keane, *Alpha-1 Foundation Ireland* Alpha-1 antitrypsin deficiency - precision medicine for COP

Leander Meuris, *VIB-UGent Center for Medical Biotechnology, Belgium* Validation of the glycomics-based glycoCirrhTest as predictor of risk of HCC development in Cirrhosis

Andreea Cislaru, *Maynooth University, Ireland* Chemoenzymatic strategy for single glycoform monoclonal antibody production

Noortje de Haan, *Amsterdam UMC, The Netherlands* Cell surface glycoproteomics to study the differential glycosylation of Cancer glycoproteins

Session 8: Glycosylation in Human Development and Disease

Andres Salumets, *Karolinska Institute, Sweden* Glycobiology of human conception

Julia Vreugdenhil, *Genos Ltd, Croatia* De novo sequencing of human milk oligo-saccharides using IM-MS

Richard Drake, *Medical University of South Carolina, USA* Detection of immune cell glycosylation as an indicator of metabolic activity in the tumour tissue microenvironment using N-glycan and multiplexed-IHC mass spectrometry imaging

Prizes

The 16th Jenner Glycobiology and Medicine Symposium organised oral presentations and poster presentations. There were six winners for poster presentations including Emily Harlin, *Maynooth University, Ireland*; Amrutha Varshini Hariharan, *CURAM, University of Galway*; Mathieu Decloquement, *University of Alberta, Canada*; Ana Costa, *University of Porto, Portugal*; Sandhya Sridhar, *Francis Crick Institute, UK* and Manuel M Vicente, *Hannover Medical School, Hannover, Germany*. The winners for oral presentations were Julia Vreugdenhi (RSC), *UMC, Netherlands* and Ines B. Moreira, *Hannover Medical School, Hannover, Germany*.

The winners of the poster presentation (left) and the winner of the oral presentation (right) at the 16th Jenner Glycobiology and Medicine Symposium in Maynooth University, Ireland.

The oral presentation competition winners for the Rising Star event included Lyndsay Young, *Medical University of South Carolina, Charleston, South Carolina, USA* and Rafaela Abrantes, *University of Porto, Porto, Portugal*.

Feedback

The 16th Jenner Glycobiology and Medicine Symposium received warm feedback from attendees. Many expressed a strong desire to join the symposium again and truly appreciated the friendly and engaging environment throughout the event. Some of the comments given included,

‘Thank you for this well-organized and inspiring conference!’

‘I loved the conference. I'm very grateful to have gotten so much knowledge from the presentations, talks, and chats with everyone! Thank you once more :)’

A special event steeped in history

The 16th Jenner Glycobiology and Medicine Symposium not only integrated the scientific community having a diverse pool of researches from all over the world but also left an unforgettable impression and created lasting lifetime memories. Highlights included an insightful interview with Prof. Pauline Rudd where she shared her personal experiences and motivated the audience members in their scientific journeys. Additionally, to make the event memorable, our chair Dr. Roisin O’Flaherty performed with her band ([The Beartlas](#)) at the dinner in Pugin Hall, Maynooth University, Ireland which was the perfect icing on the cake for many attendees. A description of the event and the abstract book of the event are available on the [16th Jenner Glycobiology and Medicine Symposium website](#). The upcoming 17th Jenner Glycobiology and Medicine will take place at the Amsterdam UMC, The Netherlands and will be chaired by Prof Yvette van Kooyk.

A selection of images of the 16th Jenner Glycobiology and Medicine Symposium including the Committee Dinner at the Carriage House, Carton House, Maynooth, Ireland (upper), an interview of Prof. Pauline Rudd by Prof. John Axford (lower left) and an eventful dinner evening at the Pugin Hall, Maynooth University, Ireland, featuring the Beartla O Flatharra Ceili Band (lower right).

Acknowledgements and Event Sponsors

The 16th Jenner Glycobiology and Medicine Symposium was made successful with the contributions from our Scientific Committee and Invited Speakers (upper left), the Organizing Committee (upper right) and Sponsors (bottom), all who played a pivotal role in ensuring the event's success.

Selected members of the Scientific Committee and Plenary Speakers (left) and the organising committee (right)

Logos of all Event Sponsors

The event was sponsored by ThermoFisher, the RSC Republic of Ireland Local Section, the RSC Carbohydrate Interest Group, Element, BioLabs, Agilent, GlycoDepot, Sciex, Ludger, Promega, the Kathleen Lonsdale Institute for Human Health Research, MU Social Sciences Institute, GlycoDiag, CÚRAM Research Ireland Centre for Medical Devices, Biochemical Journal and Eversyn. Partners included Fáilte Ireland and the Mizutani Foundation for Glycoscience.

Previous Events in this Series

The Jenner Glycobiology and Medicine symposia were the first and main international multidisciplinary conferences set up to study the relevance of glycobiology to immunology, medicine and clinical practice. The symposia have been organised, since 1990, in collaboration with the Royal Society of Medicine with the aim of widening clinical participation and to actively promote and foster fruitful interaction and collaboration between glycobiologists and clinicians. The list of events over the last two decades include:

1. *Edward Jenner's House, Bath, UK (1990).*
2. *St George's Medical School, London, UK (1992).*
3. *Il Ciocco, Italy (1994).*
4. *Loutraki, Greece (1996).*
5. *Royal Society of Medicine, London, UK (2000).*
6. *Domaine de Seillac, France (2002).*
7. *Exeter College, Oxford, UK (2004).*

8. *University College Dublin, Ireland (2007).*
9. *Académie Royale de Médecine de Belgique, Brussels (2009).*
10. *Den Haag, The Netherlands (2012).*
11. *Paris, France (2015).*
12. *Dubovnik, Croatia (2017).*
13. *Harvard University, Boston, USA (2019).*
14. *Rega Institute, KU Leuven, Belgium (2021).¹*
15. *University of Porto, Portugal (2023).*
16. *Maynooth University, Ireland (2025).*

References

- ¹ O'Flaherty, R., Opendakker, G., Clausen, H., Gerardy-Schahn, R., Kieda, C., Reis, C. A., Rudd, P. M., Sadrieh, A., Axford, J. (2022). Meeting report on 14th Jenner Glycobiology and Medicine Symposium: glycobiology in immunology, medicine, and clinical practice. *Glycobiology*, 32(6), 458-459. <https://doi.org/10.1093/glycob/cwac006>